

Methoxy-oxypalmatine.

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Späth and Bohm (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2985 and subsequent papers) reinvestigated Columba roots and isolated a substance which was chemically and crystallographically identical with palmatine. Hence they concluded that columbamine of Feist (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1907, 245, 586) is an impure specimen of palmatine, a view with which Feist seems to have agreed. By the oxidation of columbamine Feist (*loc. cit.*) obtained corydaldine and an acid which he regarded as trimethoxyphthalic acid. The constitution of this acid has been the subject matter of numerous investigations, but unanimity has not yet been reached with regard to its physical constants (*cf.* Herzig, *Annalen*, 1920, 421, 287).

3:4:5-Trimethoxy-*o*-phthalic acid has been obtained by the oxidation of colchicine by Windaus (*Sitzungsber. Heidelberger Akad. Wiss.*, 1910, 1; 1911, 1). We are synthesising this acid by a new method, the details of which will be published later on. If columbamine is identical with palmatine, Feist's acid can be either *m*-hemipinic acid or hemipinic acid.

Späth and Bohm (*loc. cit.*) attempted the synthesis of tetrahydrocolumbamine (methoxytetrahydropalmatine) by condensing 6:7-dimethoxy-1-(3':4':5'-trimethoxy) benzyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroisoquinoline and methylal. Amorphous products were obtained which consisted largely of the condensation product of two molecules of the isoquinoline with one of methylal. It has been claimed that by regulating the proportions of the reactants an amorphous base of the tetrahydroberberine type can also be obtained. But no attempt seems to have been made to isolate it in a pure condition.

We have now obtained the substance (I) by ring-closure of the amide (II), obtained from the chloride of 3:4:5-trimethoxyphthalide-carboxylic acid, and 3:5-dimethoxyphenylethylamine, by the Bischler-Napieralsky reaction. This has been converted into (III) by following a scheme analogous to Perkin, Rây and Robinson's oxyberberine synthesis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 740).

But when β -2:3:4-trimethoxyphenylethylamide of meconine carboxylic acid (IV) was subjected to Bischler-Napieralsky reaction no isoquinoline was formed in an appreciable amount. At any rate, we could not isolate any crystalline product from the reaction. It seems there is very little activation of the nuclear hydrogen atom marked (*) for ring closure. In view of this, we do not feel surprised that Späth and Bohm (*loc. cit.*) could not isolate their base of the tetrahydroberberine type in a pure condition.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

β -3:4-Dimethoxyphenylethylamine.—For this preparation the prescription of Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 403) was followed. The modification of Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2014) results in the improvement of the yield of 3:4-dimethoxyphenylpropionamide by about 4% but involves much longer time.

3:4:5-Trimethoxyphthalide carboxylic Acid.—The demethylation

observed by Alinchandani and Meldrum (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **117**, 964) can be avoided under the following circumstances:

Finely powdered gallic acid trimethyl ether (8 g.) was added in small portions and with vigorous shaking to an ice-cold solution of chloral hydrate (9 g.) in sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 50 c.c.), the temperature being maintained below 5° during addition. The mixture was left aside for 48 hours at 15-20° and then poured on to crushed ice. The precipitated trichlorophthalide was collected and extracted with boiling methyl alcohol, some bye-product remaining insoluble. On dilution with water, the methyl alcohol filtrate deposited an oil which was separated and hydrolysed with sodium hydroxide (15 g.) in water (120 c.c.) by boiling till a complete solution resulted. The well cooled solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and then kept at 70-80° for 10 minutes, when on cooling the phthalide carboxylic acid separated in colourless needles, yield 7 g. The substance crystallises from water with a molecule of water of crystallisation, m.p. (after drying), 147°. (Found: C, 53.54; H, 4.68. $C_{12}H_{12}O_7$ requires C, 53.64; H, 4.92 per cent).

The Amide (II).—3:4:5-Trimethoxyphthalide carboxylic acid (2 g.) dissolved in dry benzene was treated with thionyl chloride (4 c.c.) and the mixture kept at 50-60° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After removal of the volatile matter in *vacuo*, the residue was treated with fresh benzene and the solvent again removed in *vacuo*. Finally the residue was heated at 100° for a few minutes in *vacuo* and then dissolved in benzene (10 c.c.). The solution of the acid chloride was mixed with a solution of β -3:4-dimethoxyphenylethylamine (1.3 g.) and pyridine (0.6 g.) in dry benzene (10 c.c.) with cooling and left aside for 2 hours. After washing successively with water, dilute hydrochloric acid, dilute ammonia and again with water, the solvent was removed from the benzene layer. The residue crystallised from alcohol in plates, m.p. 154°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 3.4. $C_{22}H_{25}O_8N$ requires N, 3.25 per cent).

The isoQuinoline (I).—The foregoing amide (2 g.) in phosphoryl chloride (20 c.c.) was very gently heated on the steam-bath for 5 hours. The temperature of the reaction mixture was not allowed to rise above 60°. The solution was decomposed with crushed ice and left aside for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then filtered from a tarry impurity. The well cooled bright yellow filtrate was basified below 10°. The ochreous yellow precipitate was well washed, dried in *vacuo* over sodium hydroxide and then dissolved in ethyl acetate. The residual isoquinoline from the filtered ethyl acetate solution was used directly for conversion into the methoxyoxypalmatine (III), yield 40%.

Methoxy-oxypalmatine (III).—The crude isoquinoline, obtained above, was reduced with zinc dust (7 g.) added in small amounts in glacial acetic acid solution by boiling for about 10 minutes. The reduction of the dihydroisoquinoline to the tetrahydro stage was accompanied by a change of colour from brown to pale yellow, a bluish green fluorescence developing. The solution filtered from zinc dust was diluted with ethyl acetate and the solution washed well with water to remove acetic acid and then the solvent removed from the ethyl acetate layer. The oily residue was dissolved in alcohol (10 c.c.) and treated with sodium hydroxide (2 g.) in water (4 c.c.) and the mixture warmed on the steam-bath for 5 minutes. On pouring into water (150 c.c.) methoxy-oxypalmatine was precipitated in a crystalline form. Recrystallised from hot aqueous alcohol it had m.p. 170°. (Found: C, 66.01; H, 6.07. $C_{22}H_{25}O_6N$ requires C, 66.16; H, 6.26 per cent.)

A solution of the substance in neutral solvents has a pale yellow colour with a strong greenish blue fluorescence. A solution in 50% sulphuric acid gives with a drop of nitric acid a permanganate-violet colour which is discharged on dilution.

β -2 : 3 : 4-Trimethoxyphenylethylamine was prepared according to the method of Slottar and Heller (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 3040) but we are unable to confirm the statement that the action of sodium hypochlorite on β -2 : 3 : 4-trimethoxyphenylpropionamide results in the production of a horny mass.

Trimethoxyphenylpropionamide (10 g.) was added in small portions to a solution of sodium hypochlorite, prepared with chlorine generated from potassium permanganate (3.5 g.) and hydrochloric acid (excess) and absorbed in 110 c.c. of 10% sodium hydroxide solution at 0°. After the whole of the amide had passed into solution the mixture was heated at 70° for 1 hour. It was then hydrolysed with sodium hydroxide (40 g.) at 70-80°. The liberated amine was extracted with benzene, dried and solvent removed. The crude amine was converted into the hydrochloride or the oxalate, m.p. 185°, after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 4.62. $C_{13}H_{19}O_7N$ requires N, 4.65 per cent.)

The β -2 : 3 : 4-trimethoxyphenylethylamide of meconine carboxylic acid, prepared in the usual manner, gave very minute trace of an uncrystallisable basic material which resisted purification.